

Quantum $\exp(ipx)$ from Classical Considerations, Special Relativity and Discontinuities

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We try to argue that the idea of probability associated with motion may have classical beginnings in that the center-of-mass (cm) of a piece of mass moving with constant velocity v is present within a dx at some time, but moves out of dx . Flux is constant, but at one time the particle cm leaves dx and arrives at the adjacent dx . Constant flux suggests one does not need to consider time. In such a case, one might associate a periodic function showing probability being removed from a region dx (at x) (i.e. a negative distribution) followed by it being added (a positive distribution) to a region $x+dx$. This suggests a negative-positive cycle, but this labels certain x regions as negative and others as positive which is inconsistent with all x regions having the same weight based on a constant v . Given that time is removed, it seems this cycling may have nothing to do with velocity v or perhaps anything else for that matter. As a result, one may postulate an $A\exp(ibx)$, where b is a constant, for motion. We will argue for a phase linear in x . $A\exp(-ibx)\exp(ipx)$ yields a constant AA , which is flux, and treats all x points the same.

At this point, one cannot go farther unless one considers other issues. We consider two such issues. First we ask what happens if the particle is viewed from a frame moving at constant v ? The velocity of the particle will not be the same, but we have argued that $\exp(ibx')$ may be the form, yielding no information about b when (x,t) changes to (x',t') . If on the other hand, the phase cannot change if the particle is viewed from the moving frame, one requires a Lorentz invariant. This suggests that the phase may actually be $-Et+px$. (We also show that it is not necessary to use special relativity to obtain the form $\exp(ipx)$. Rather one may consider ideas of pressure balance associated with continuity of $\exp(ibx)$.)

As a second consideration, we examine a one dimensional reflection-refraction problem at a point x_0 for which a probability equation $1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract})$ exists. If $\exp(ipx)$ for constant E describes motion, this motion changes with changing p , yet one wishes probability to be a continuous function at x_0 . This suggests different weight coefficients for different $\exp(ipx)$ which seem to be associated with $P(\text{reflect})$, and $P(\text{refract})$. If $x=0$, one has an equation in the weights, with $A+B$ ($x < x_0$) matching C ($x > x_0$) at x_0 . If one stops at this point, $\exp(ipx)$ does not seem to have any impact. One may note, however, that in general x_0 is not zero and that one wishes at the very least to have the derivatives match. This immediately links the A, B, C values to the p (momentum) discontinuity. Thus using special relativity to create an $\exp(ipx)$ has practical implications because it allows one to deal with p discontinuities.

We also show though that special relativity, i.e the use of $-Et+px$, may be bypassed and the form $A\exp(ipx)$ obtained as a result of its first derivative yielding p which is needed in a pressure balance equation. This then suggests A is the square root of flux.

Classical Arguments for an $\exp(ibx)$ Description of Motion

Motion of a particle with a constant velocity may be mapped into a steady stream motion, which does not require time. This means one may think of the problem using only x (even though $\text{velocity} = x/t$ is present). Velocity is linear in x and we retain this linear feature of x , but with time removed, one must only use x to describe motion. In such a case, one may argue that

the center-of-mass is removed from one dx and moved to the next. This suggests a negative x distribution, linear in x, in some set of dx region, followed by the same positive distribution in the adjacent dx region. This pattern should be repeated to +/- infinite.

An immediate problem with this picture is that certain x values are associated with the removal of probability and others with the addition., when all x values should have the same weight for a constant v. Furthermore, there is the issue of time. A negative distribution followed by a positive one should be associated with a dt, the time in which the particle probability is removed from dx and added to the adjoining dx. The steady stream picture, however, does not require time, but only a flux, which may be a coefficient of the periodic x distribution. This suggests that the periodic function must be linked with the constant 1. This, in turn, suggests a complex number with a coefficient linked to flux i.e.

$$A \exp(ibx) \rightarrow AA \exp(ibx) \exp(-ibx) = AA \quad ((1)) \quad \text{Time is in the flux AA.}$$

In other words, one obtains a square root flux probability multiplied by a complex $\exp(ibx)$. Here we assume a constant b in $\exp(ibx)$ because there is no knowledge as to what it is. One might argue that it is velocity dependent and not a constant at all. At this point, one may proceed no further unless one introduces other ideas.

We suggest that an important idea is the phase value $\exp(ibx)$. If a particle is viewed from a frame moving with constant v, x,t becomes x',t', but one might expect the phase to remain constant. This actually links a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t with all various E', p', x', t', v' values so the constant phase is a way of saying that there is an equivalence between the particle as seen in the various different moving frames. As a result, special relativity suggests motion be described by:

$$A \exp(-iEt + ipx) \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where A is square root flux (i.e includes velocity considerations)}$$

Discontinuities in Momentum

One may ask: Of what practical use is ((2))? We suggest one immediate use in the situation of discontinuities in p. Consider a particle with energy E and momentum p_1 moving in a constant potential V_1 . If at $x=x_0$, this potential changes to a different constant V_2 and E remains constant, one may expect reflection and refraction, i.e. there will be a p_2 for $x > x_0$. This is again a flux problem with square root flux (associated with v) included in the coefficient of $\exp(ipx)$. One would expect this new square root flux to be continuous at $x=x_0$ as well as its first derivative. Given that the first derivative yields p (momentum) values and the coefficient of $\exp(ipx)$ is linked with square root flux, one may see that ultimately a pressure expression may result from the two continuity equations. Thus:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x) \quad \text{at } x=x_0 \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$A p \exp(ipx) - B p \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2x) \quad \text{at } x=x_0 \quad ((3b))$$

The picture of probability removal and addition in space, linked with special relativity, yields a kind of square-root flux probability which handles discontinuities in p at x .

Flux is Not Enough

A key point in the above analysis is that the notion of flux is not enough. A steady stream (flux) is a constant, yet each single particle has its center-of-mass removed from one dx and added to the next (adjacent) one. This physical reality must be included and must be consistent with the constant flux scenario. It seems this may only be done by using a complex phase expression $\exp(ibx)$. Then $A\exp(ipx) \rightarrow AA\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = AA$ yields a constant flux. The fluxes AA, BB, CC (incident, reflected, refracted beams) when multiplied by p 's should yield a pressure balance equation, suggesting that $\exp(ibx)$ may actually be $\exp(ipx)$ (without using special relativity). In other words, one requires continuity of the $A\exp(ibx)$ type probability with weights and its derivative, but multiplying the two (or the complex conjugate of one with the second) may yield a pressure equation which requires a linear p . This p should come from the first derivative $-i d/dx$. Thus $-id/dx$ becomes associated with p .

In other words, even though special relativistic arguments were used above, they are not needed a priori. One may use the form $\exp(ipx)$, continuity of $A\exp(ipx)$ s and their derivative, and the goal of ultimately obtaining a pressure balance equation to suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ is the correct form. This may then be linked to the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that classical thinking leads to the quantum $\exp(ipx)$ form. We suggest that a particle moving with a constant velocity may be thought of in two equivalent forms. First, it may be represented by a flux (which incorporates the time aspects). The constant value shows that all x points are treated the same. Secondly, a moving particle removes center-of-mass probability at dx and adds it to the adjacent dx . This suggests a negative-positive distribution in all of space which treats different x points differently. For the constant flux to be consistent with this picture, we suggest the form $A\exp(ipx)$ where b is some constant or possibly a function of velocity etc. Then, $AA\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = AA = \text{flux}$.

If one considers a discontinuity in p values at $x=x_0$, i.e. a reflection-refraction type problem for a particle moving from constant potential V_1 to V_2 with E constant, one wishes to have the $A\exp(ipx)$ form and its derivative continuous at $x=x_0$. The complex conjugate of one equation multiplied by the second should give a pressure balance at $x=x_0$. The coefficient AA etc yields flux, so one requires momentum p for pressure. Thus, $b=p$ is a solution and $-idd/x$ yields p . Alternatively, the form $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ may be obtained using special relativistic considerations.